

New Constituents and Biological Activity of the Roots of *Murraya koenigii*

SANTOSH K. SRIVASTAVA* and SAVITRI D. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Doctor Hari Singh Gour University, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 28 July 1992, accepted 8 February 1993

Murraya koenigii is a small tree with dark grey bark native to India at the foot of the Himalaya from Kumanu to Sikkim and bears various medicinal properties¹. Previous chemical study of this species include reports of various alkaloids². The present communication deals with a detailed examination of root extracts of *M. koenigii* and reports the isolation of three new compounds, murrayenol (1), murrayagetin (2) and marmesin-1''-O-rutinoside (3) alongwith known substances epilupeol and umbelliferone. Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antifecadant activities of the root extract have also been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

Compound 1, m.p. 234–36^o, C₃₀H₄₆O₄ (M⁺ 470), was indicated as protolimonoid by its ¹H nmr spectrum which displayed at high field a set of signals which could be related to seven methyl groups. It possesses hydroxy group as revealed by ir band at 3 350 cm⁻¹ by two-proton nmr signals at δ 4.20 and 3.90 which disappeared on exchange with D₂O as well as by the formation of a diacetate (1a) and confirmed by ¹H nmr spectrum of 1a. The hemiacetal structure (1) was confirmed by oxidation with chromium trioxide in pyridine yielding the five-membered ring lactone (1b) characterised by a ir band at 1 770 cm⁻¹. Compound 1 showed the ¹H nmr spectrum characteristic for an allylic alcohol type grouping in ring-A as observed earlier³. The occurrence of fourth oxygen atom in an oxiran ring in 1 was disclosed by a signal for an epoxide proton at δ 2.90 (d, J 7.50 Hz) and a peak M⁺ -71 in the mass spectrum for the loss of C₃H₇O as

well as a peak m/z 71 corresponding to $\text{HC}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ structure. Compound 1 is closely related structurally to melianol, melianone and turraecanthin⁴. Although ¹H and ¹³C nmr (Tables 1 and 2) spectra of 1 were consistent with the structure shown, additional information was required for complete elucidation of the structure

by the following sets of chemical reaction. Compound 1 on treatment with 5% Pd-C afforded melianol, m.p. 193–95^o, [α]_D-40^o (lit. 194–95^o, [α]_D-38^o)⁴ which on CrO-C₅H₅N oxidation afforded 3-turraecanthinone-γ-lactone (melianone lactone), m.p. 156–67^o, [α]_D-50^o (lit. 165–66^o, [α]_D-48^o)⁴. Thus murrayenol was assigned by the structure 1.

(1) R = H

(1a) R = Ac

(1b)

Compound 2, m.p. 126–28^o, C₁₉H₂₀O₄ (M⁺ 312), gave fluorescence under uv-light indicative for a coumarin⁵. It was found to be soluble in alkali giving a yellow solution from which it could be regenerated by acidification, indicating the presence of a δ-lactone characterised by the ir bands at 1 710 and 1 630 cm⁻¹. Its uv spectrum showed absorptions at 320, 240 and 215 nm, characteristic for 7-oxygenated coumarin⁶. It was closely related in structure (2) as evidenced by comparison of their ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (Tables 1 and 2). The obvious similarity includes four quaternary methyls singlets, an aldehydic singlet, methine triplet, a methylene doublet, two separate ortho-coupled aromatic doublets and two separate lactone ring

TABLE 1—¹H NMR ASSIGNMENTS FOR COMPOUNDS 1, 2 AND 3a*

Proton	1	2	3a	Proton	1	2	3a
H-1	6.20d(10)	—	—	Me-18	0.70s	—	—
H-2	6.55dd(6.10)	—	—	Me-19	0.80s	—	—
H-3	3.95d(6)	6.10d(9.50)	6.20d(9.50)	Me-26	1.30s	—	—
H-4	—	7.60d(9.50)	7.60d(9.50)	Me-27	1.30s	—	—
H-5	—	7.35d(9.50)	6.50s	Me-28	1.00s	—	—
H-6	—	6.80d(8.50)	—	Me-29	1.10s	—	—
H-7	5.38m	—	—	Me-30	1.15s	—	—
H-8	—	—	7.20s	Me-4'	—	1.78s	—
H-21	5.30s	—	—	Me-5'	—	1.80s	—
H-23	3.80m	—	—	Me-9'	—	1.70s	—
H-24	2.90d(7.5)	—	—	Me-10'	—	2.30s	—
3-OH	4.20s	—	—	Me-2''	—	—	1.25s
21-OH	3.90s	—	—	Me-3''	—	—	1.30s
H-1'	—	4.60d(7)	—	Gluc H-1	—	—	5.10d(7)
H-2'	—	5.50t(7)	4.70t(8.50)	Rham H-1	—	—	4.50d(2)
H-3'	—	—	3.20d(7)	Rham Me	—	—	1.20d(6)
H-6'	—	10.10s	—	Sugar OAC	—	—	1.95, 1.98, 2.00, 2.10, 2.15 and 2.18s
				Other sugar H	—	—	5.80-5.50m

*Number in paranthesis represents the coupling constant in Hz.

TABLE 2—¹³C NMR ASSIGNMENTS FOR COMPOUNDS 1, 2 AND 3a

Carbon	1	2	3a	Carbon	1	2	3
C-1	158.00	—	—	C-29	15.90	—	—
C-2	125.40	160.80	161.00	C-30	25.50	—	—
C-3	204.20	112.80	112.20	C-1'	—	34.50	91.00
C-4	43.60	143.45	143.50	C-2'	—	123.30	28.50
C-5	40.00	128.50	128.00	C-3'	—	135.70	—
C-6	23.00	107.50	112.00	C-4'	—	17.80	—
C-7	123.70	159.50	63.00	C-5'	—	25.70	—
C-8	154.00	113.00	101.20	C-6'	—	188.50	—
C-9	46.20	—	—	C-7'	—	129.00	—
C-10	39.20	—	—	C-8'	—	152.40	—
C-11	72.20	—	—	C-9'	—	24.70	—
C-12	42.70	—	—	C-10'	—	19.60	—
C-13	46.50	—	—	Gluc C-1	—	—	101.50
C-14	158.50	—	—	C-2	—	—	69.00
C-15	119.20	—	—	C-3	—	—	78.80
C-16	35.00	—	—	C-4	—	—	64.00
C-17	52.00	—	—	C-5	—	—	77.00
C-18	16.40	—	—	C-6	—	—	63.00
C-19	22.50	—	—	Rham C-1	—	—	100.50
C-20	157.30	—	—	C-2	—	—	70.50
C-21	95.90	—	—	C-3	—	—	70.90
C-22	119.30	—	—	C-4	—	—	72.20
C-23	67.40	—	—	C-5	—	—	68.00
C-24	44.00	—	—	C-6	—	—	17.50
C-25	29.50	—	—	OCOCH ₃	—	—	160.00
C-26	27.50	—	—	OCOCH ₃	—	—	21.00
C-27	27.50	—	—	C-1''	—	—	58.00
C-28	22.90	—	—	C-2'' (Me)	—	—	17.40
				C-3'' (Me)	—	—	17.20
				C-4a	—	112.20	112.50
				C-8a	—	160.00	159.90

doublets. Additional structural support of **2** was obtained by acid hydrolysis yielding a product which on treatment with Me₂SO₄-K₂CO₃ afforded murralongin

(m.m.p., co-tlc and spectral data)⁷. Thus murrayagetin was assigned by the structure **2**.

Compound **3**, m.p. 190-91⁰, C₂₀H₃₄O₁₃ res-

ponded positive reaction to glycoside and gave a fluorescence under uv-light, indicative of a coumarin glycoside⁸. Acid hydrolysis of **3** afforded glucose and rhamnose as sugar components and marmesin as aglycone part. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data of the aglycone were compared with the published data^{9,10} and the aglycone was confirmed as marmesin (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁹. Compound **3** formed an acetate **3a** (Ac₂O-C₃H₅N), the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of which displayed signals characteristic for rutinose sugar, α-linkage between glucose and rhamnose and β-linkage between glucose and marmesin. Partial acid hydrolysis yielded L-rhamnose, followed by D-glucose indicating the presence of rhamnose as the terminal sugar. Compound **3** when methylated using Me₂SO₄-K₂CO₃ followed by acid hydrolysis yielded marmesin, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl derivatives of rhamnose and glucose respectively, supporting the rutinose moiety. From these results the structure of **3** was elucidated as marmesin-1''-*O*-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→6)-β-D-glucopyranoside.

Bioassay : The antibacterial activity (Table 3) of the EtOH extract of roots of *M. koenigii* was assayed by filter paper disc method¹¹ against *Vibrio cholerae* (VC), *Salmonella typhimurium* (ST) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA). Streptomycin was used as a standard. The extract showed the positive effect on all the tested organisms.

The antiinflammatory activity of the extract (Table 3) was evaluated in albino rats (100–120 g, fasted overnight) by carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method¹². The percentage inhibition of inflam-

mation after 5 h was calculated¹³. Oxyphenbutazone was used as a standard.

The antifeedant activity (Table 3) of the extract was determined by the reported method¹¹ against 3rd instar grub stages of brinjal beetle, *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata Fabricius*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra (EtOH) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on CFT-20 (90 MHz) and Bruker WM 400 (90.56 MHz) spectrometers respectively, using TMS a internal standard, and mass spectra on a JMS D-300 spectrometer equipped with a direct inlet system operating at 70 eV.

Extraction and isolation : Roots (2 kg) of *M. koenigii* (procured from United Chemical and Allied Products, Calcutta) were refluxed with EtOH. The EtOH extract was concentrated to get a solid mass which was then successively extracted with petroleum ether and benzene. The petroleum ether extract was subjected to column chromatography on a glass column (70 × 6 cm) packed with silica gel. Eluting solvents were hexane-petroleum ether (5 : 5), petroleum ether-benzene (5 : 5) and benzene respectively, to afford epilupeol and compounds **1** (900 mg) and **2** (600 mg). The benzene extract was also column chromatographed over silica gel and eluted with C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (8 : 2) and C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (3 : 7) respectively, to yield umbelliferone and compound **3** (700 mg). The monitoring of the fraction was carried out on silica gel plates. The known compounds on detailed studies were found to be epilupeol and umbelliferone respectively (spectral data, m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁸.

Compound **1** gave $\nu_{\max}$ at 3 350, 1 630, 1 240, 1 030, 970 and 820 cm⁻¹ (Found C, 76.42; H, 9.58. C₃₀H₄₆O₁ requires : C, 76.59; H, 9.78%). The acetate (**1a**) was prepared from murrayenol (100 mg) in pyridine (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml), kept at reflux temperature for 40 min. Addition of water produced an amorphous solid which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 183–84⁰; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 720 cm⁻¹ (acetate); ¹H nmr δ 6.60 (H-2), 6.30 (H-21), 6.20 (H-1), 5.40 (H-7), 5.00 (H-3), 3.80 (H-23), 2.90 (H-24), 1.30, 1.30,

TABLE 3—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF THE EtOH EXTRACT

Microorga- nisms	Antibacterial activity*		Anti-inflammatory activity.				Antifeedant activity**						
	Extract		Group	Dose mg/kg per OS	Total increase in paw vol. after 5 h.	% Inhi- bition	19.5 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$		6 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$		2.0 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$		
	10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$					2 days	6 days	2 days	6 days	2 days	6 days	
VT	+++	++	Control	—	0.43±0.02	—	Extract	++	++	+	+	+	-
ST	+++	++	Extract	1000	0.17±0.04	60.46	Check	-	-	-	-	-	-
SA	+++	+++	Oxyphen- butazone	100	0.12±0.02	72.09							
Standard	++++	++++											

* (++) = 9–15 mm, (+++) = 16–23 mm. (++++) = 24–30 mm. **Corresponds to feeding control : (++) = 30–40%, (+) = 20–30%. (-) = 0.20%; % feeding = 100 [1 - (% feeding / % feeding by stock)].

1.20, 1.15, 0.80 and 0.70 ($7 \times \text{Me}$); 2.10 and 2.20 ($2 \times \text{OAc}$).

Formation of 1b : Murrayenol (200 mg) in $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (5 ml) was mixed with a solution of CrO_3 (200 mg in 10 ml of $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$) and the solution was stirred for 30 h at room temperature. Water and dilute HCl were then added to pH 3 and the product was extracted with ether. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was chromatographed and **1b** (100 mg) was eluted from silica gel column (petroleum ether-benzene, 5 : 5), m.p. 140–42° (Found : C, 77.18; H, 8.92. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.25; H, 9.00%); ν_{max} 1 770, 1 710, 1 635, 1 150 and 825 cm^{-1} .

Hydrogenation of murrayenol : Murrayenol (200 mg) in methanol (50 ml) was hydrogenated over prerduced 5% Pd-C (80 mg). Uptake of 1 mol was complete after 30 min. The melianol was crystallised from acetone-methanol as prismatic needles (Found : C, 76.13; H, 10.00; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 76.27; H, 10.16%); λ_{max} 212 nm (ϵ 2 700); ν_{max} 3 580, 3 450, 1 625, 1 030, 985 and 830 cm^{-1} .

The latter product (80 mg) in $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (2 ml) was mixed with a solution of CrO_3 (80 mg in 5 ml $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$) and worked up as usual to yield melianone lactone which was crystallised from ether as colourless needles (Found : C, 76.70; H, 9.28; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 76.92; H, 9.40%); λ_{max} 210 nm (ϵ 2 500); ν_{max} 1 775, 1 712, 1 630, 1 165, 1 150 and 830 cm^{-1} .

Compound **2** showed ν_{max} at 1 710, 1 660, 1 630, 1 620, 1 600 and 1 370 cm^{-1} (Found : C, 72.90; H, 6.18. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 73.07; H, 6.41%).

Acid hydrolysis and methylation on 2 : Compound

2 (200 mg) in MeOH (25 ml) was treated with 7% HCl (10 ml) and worked up¹⁵ as usual to give the product (ether), m.p. 180–82°, which gave positive test with FeCl_3 . The latter compound (100 mg) was treated with Me_2SO_4 (5 ml) and K_2CO_3 (2 g) in dry acetone (15 ml) and worked up⁸ as usual to give light yellow crystals (CHCl_3), m.p. 135–37°, corresponding to that of murrayenol (m.p. 135–36°); ^1H nmr δ 10.10 (s, CHO), 7.50 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.30 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-5), 6.10 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 6.80 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-6), 3.80 (s, OCH_3), 2.30 and 1.70 (each s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ 188.00 (C-1'), 161.00 (C-2), 160.00 (C-8a), 159.00 (C-7), 153.00, (C-2'), 143.50 (C-4), 129.00 (CHO), 128.00 (C-5), 113.00 (C-4a), 113.5 (C-8), 112.00 (C-3), 108.00 (C-6), 56 (OCH_3), 24.50 (CH_3) and 19.80 (CH_3).

Compound **3** showed ν_{max} at 3 300 (OH), 1 700, 1 625, 1 590, 1 400, 1 350, 1 270, 1 120, 950 and 820 (Found : C, 56.28; H, 6.00. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_{13}$ requires : C, 56.31; H, 6.13%).

Acid hydrolysis of 3 : Compound **3** (800 mg) was hydrolysed with 7% H_2SO_4 (40 ml) by refluxing 5 h. The resulting solid was washed with water to afford marmesin and the aqueous portion was found to contain D-glucose and L-rhamnose (co-*pc*); marmesin; ^1H nmr δ 7.70 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.20 (s, H-8), 6.40 (s, H-5), 6.30 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 4.80 (t, J 8.50 Hz, H-2'), 3.20 (d, J 7.00 Hz, H-3'), 1.85 (s, OH), 1.30 and 1.20 (each s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ 161.00 (C-2), 158.80 (C-8a), 143.20 (C-4), 128.00 (C-5), 112.50 (C-4a), 112.20 (C-3), 112.00 (C-6), 101.00 (C-8), 91.20 (C-2'), 63.00 (C-7), 58.00 (C-1'), 28.40 (C-3'), 17.35

(CH₃) and 17.25 (CH₃).

Partial acid hydrolysis of 3 : Compound **3** (200 mg) in EtOH (15 ml) was hydrolysed with 7% H₂SO₄ (20 ml) at reflux temperature for 30 min to give L-rhamnose (co-pc) and marmesin-1''-O-glucoside. The latter compound on further hydrolysis (3 h) yielded marmesin (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-glucose (co-pc).

Permethylation of 3 followed by acid hydrolysis : Permethylation of **3** (200 mg) was done using Me₂SO₄ (6 ml) and K₂CO₃ (2 g) in EtOH (20 ml) for 6 h and worked up as usual⁸ to give light yellow needles (MeOH), m.p. 130–32°. A solution of the permethyl ether (100 mg) in 5% HCl-MeOH (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated, diluted with H₂O, and filtered and resulting solid was crystallised from MeOH to give marmesin (m.m.p. and co-tlc). The filtrate was neutralised with Ag₂CO₃, filtered and concentrated. The residue was found to be a mixture of 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose by RG.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank to Director, R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for spectral and analytical measurements. This work is a part of research project sponsoring by U.G.C., New Delhi for which one of the authors (S.K.S.) is grateful.

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